

Commentary

Treatment using Kampo medicine (*Keigai-rengyo-to* or *Seijo-bofu-to*) for human metapneumovirus infection

Short title: Treatment using Kampo medicine for human metapneumovirus infection

Masashi Ohe (ORCID number, 0000-0002-6684-6688)

Department of Internal Medicine, JCHO Hokkaido Hospital, Sapporo, Japan

Corresponding author: Masashi Ohe: e-mail: oektsp1218@sweet.ocn.ne.jp

Department of Internal Medicine, JCHO Hokkaido Hospital

1-8-3-18 Nakanoshima, Toyohira-ku, Sapporo 062-8618, Japan

Abstract

Human metapneumovirus (hMPV) is a globally prevalent respiratory pathogen that primarily affects young children, older adults, and immunocompromised individuals. Since its discovery in 2001, hMPV has been recognized as a major cause of upper and lower respiratory tract infections, with clinical features resembling those of respiratory syncytial virus. Nearly all children are exposed by age five, and seasonal peaks occur in late winter to early spring in temperate regions such as Japan. Severe disease, including bronchiolitis and pneumonia, is most common in infants, the elderly, and immunocompromised patients. Although management is supportive care, no antiviral agents are currently licensed for hMPV. Ribavirin and remdesivir show *in vitro* antiviral activity, but their clinical efficacy remains uncertain. Recent *in silico* studies suggest that several herbal medicines may inhibit hMPV. Glycyrrhizin from *Glycyrrhiza Radix* binds strongly to the hMPV F protein, while quercetin and rutin from *Forsythia Fructus*, epigallocatechin gallate from *Camellia sinensis*, and apigenin from *Schizonepetae Spica* exhibit binding affinity for the hMPV F and/or N protein. In Japan, Kampo medicines containing these ingredients—particularly *Keigai-rengyo-to* and *Seijo-bofu-to*—may therefore have therapeutic potential. Further *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and clinical studies are required to evaluate their safety and efficacy as potential treatments for hMPV.

Keywords: human metapneumovirus, phytochemicals, Kampo medicine

Human metapneumovirus (hMPV) is a globally circulating respiratory pathogen that primarily affects young children, older adults, and immunocompromised individuals. Since its discovery in 2001, it has been recognized as a major cause of both upper and lower respiratory tract infections, often presenting with clinical features similar to those caused by respiratory syncytial virus (RSV). hMPV infections occur worldwide, and nearly all children are exposed by the age of five. In temperate regions, including Japan, seasonal peaks typically occur from late winter to early spring. The virus contributes substantially to pediatric hospitalizations—particularly among children under one year of age—and can exacerbate chronic respiratory diseases in adults. hMPV belongs to the *Pneumoviridae* family and is closely related to RSV. It is an enveloped, negative-sense, single-stranded RNA virus. Its structural proteins include the fusion (F) protein, attachment (G) protein, nucleoprotein (N), phosphoprotein (P), matrix (M) protein, and polymerase (L) protein, all of which mediate viral entry, replication, and assembly. Typical symptoms include cough, fever, nasal congestion, and shortness of breath. In severe cases—especially among infants and older adults—hMPV can cause bronchiolitis, pneumonia, asthma exacerbations, and worsening of COPD. Reinfections occur throughout life, although symptoms are generally milder. Most healthy individuals recover within several days to two weeks, whereas severe disease is more likely in infants, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals. Hospitalization may be required for respiratory distress,

dehydration, or complications such as secondary bacterial infections.

Management is supportive and includes oxygen therapy, hydration, and treatment of complications.

Although no antiviral drugs are currently licensed for hMPV, ribavirin exhibits antiviral activity *in vitro* and in animal models. However, its clinical utility is limited by toxicity and inconsistent outcomes. Broad-spectrum antivirals such as remdesivir—originally developed for *Ebola* virus and SARS-CoV-2—demonstrate laboratory activity against hMPV and may be useful in severe or mixed viral infections [1]. Clinical trials are required to establish their safety and therapeutic efficacy before formal approval.

In addition to these agents, herbal medicines may offer practical therapeutic alternatives. *In silico* analyses have demonstrated that glycyrrhizin, an extract of *Glycyrrhiza Radix*, shows strong binding affinity to the hMPV F protein (PDB ID: 5WB0) [2]. Similarly, quercetin and rutin—extracts of *Forsythia Fructus*—exhibit binding affinity for the hMPV F protein, a key mediator of membrane fusion and an essential factor in viral entry and assembly [3]. Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), derived from *Camellia sinensis*, also demonstrates *in silico* binding affinity for the F protein [3]. Furthermore, apigenin, an extract of *Schizonepetae Spica*, shows high binding affinity for both the hMPV F and N protein, the latter of which encapsidates and protects the viral genome [4]. These findings suggest that *Glycyrrhiza Radix*, *Forsythia*

Fructus, Camellia sinensis, and Schizonepetae Spica are promising candidates for hMPV inhibition.

In Japan, the national insurance system allows clinicians to prescribe herbal medicines as Japanese Kampo medicines (KMs) efficiently and at low cost. KMs—including *Kakkon-to* (KT), *Sho-saiko-to* (SST), and *Saiko-keishi-to* (SKT)—are traditional formulations derived from traditional Chinese medicine. Approximately 150 KMs are commercially available in Japan, and they are widely prescribed for conditions such as the common cold, pulmonary and hepatic diseases, urological and dermatologic disorders, menopausal symptoms, and dementia. KMs primarily consist of plant-derived ingredients, including *Scutellariae Radix, Ziziphus jujuba, Glycyrrhiza Radix, Forsythia Fructus, Camellia sinensis, Schizonepetae Spica, and Panax ginseng* (Table 1). For example, SST contains *Scutellariae Radix, Glycyrrhiza Radix, Ziziphus jujuba, Panax ginseng, Bupleurum Radix, Pinelliae Tuber, and Zingiberis Rhizoma* (Table 1). During the COVID-19 pandemic, KMs—including KT, SST, *Sho-saiko-to-ka-kikyo-sekko* (SSTKS), SKT, and *Keigai-rengyo-to* (KRT)—were successfully used clinically, with or without concomitant minocycline [5–8]. Considering their antiviral and anti-inflammatory properties, KT, SST, SSTKS, SKT, KRT, and *Seijo-bofu-to* (SBT) have been used or proposed as potential treatments for influenza, monkeypox, severe fever with thrombocytopenia syndrome, Crimean–Congo hemorrhagic fever, dengue fever, Chikungunya

virus infection, Zika virus infection, and RSV infection [9–16]. According to Table 1, both KRT and SBT contain *Glycyrrhiza Radix*, *Forsythia Fructus*, and *Schizonepetae Spica*; therefore, these two KMs may have therapeutic potential against hMPV. Clinicians in Japan typically prescribe KRT for chronic-phase rhinitis, sinusitis, and acne, whereas SBT is used for acute-phase acne. KRT contains 1.5 g of *Forsythia Fructus* (vs. 2.5 g in SBT) and 1.5 g of *Schizonepetae Spica* (vs. 1.0 g in SBT) (Table 1). These quantitative differences may influence their relative antiviral potential.

In any case, *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and clinical studies are required to establish the safety and therapeutic efficacy of these two KMs before they can be officially approved for hMPV treatment.

Funding: No funding

Declaration of interest: The authors have no conflicts of interest associated with this article.

References

1. Pandey V, Shahi P, Kolios G, Uddin MI, Spathakis M, Collins AR, Paspaliaris V, Rai AK. Human metapneumovirus (hMPV): the virus who came with the common cold. *Infection*. 2026 Feb;54(1):1-3.

2. Dubey A, Kumar M, Tufail A, Dwivedi VD, Ragusa A. Unlocking antiviral potentials of traditional plants: A multi-method computational study against human metapneumovirus (HMPV). *Journal of infection and public health*. 2025 Oct 1;18(10):102885.
3. Dubey A, Kumar M, Tufail A. Suppressing viral assembly in human metapneumovirus by targeting fusion protein with natural compounds: a structural dynamics and energetics study. *Journal of Molecular Modeling*. 2026 May;32(5):146.
4. Rahaman HH, Khan A, Sharif N, Ahmed W, Sharif N, Majumder R, Obregon SA, Iglesias RC, De la Torre Díez I, Dey SK. In silico prediction, molecular docking and simulation of natural flavonoid apigenin and xanthoangelol E against human metapneumovirus. *In Silico Pharmacology*. 2026 Jan 27;14(1):40.
5. Takayama S, Namiki T, Arita R, et al. Multicenter, randomized controlled trial of traditional Japanese medicine, kakkonto with shosaikotokakikyosekko, for mild and moderate coronavirus disease patients. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022 Nov 9;13:1008946.
6. Ohe M, Shida H, Yamamoto J, et al. COVID-19 Treated with Minocycline and Saiko-keishi-to: A Case Report. *Intern Med J*. 2024;31:27-8.
7. Ohe M, Shida H, Yamamoto J, Seki M, Furuya K. Successful treatment with minocycline and Saiko-keishi-to for COVID-19. *J CLIN EXP INVEST*. 2023;14(2): em00815. <https://doi.org/10.29333/jcei/12999>

8. Yanagi K, Suzuki M, Hasegawa S. *Shingata koronairusu kansen-shō (COVID-19) no innaikansen ni taisuru keigairengyoto no hassho yobo koka* [Preventive effect of Keigairengyoto on nosocomial infection of COVID-19]. *Kampo to Saishin Chiryō*, 2020;29(2):131–6.
9. Tsuchida N, Ohe M. Treatment with Kampo Medicine and Minocycline for Influenza. *Intern Med J.* 2025;32:162-3.
10. Ohe M. Drug Repurposing with Minocycline and Japanese Kampo Medicine for Mpox: Predicting Efficacy through In Silico Studies. *Intern Med J.* 2025;32:2-3.
11. Ohe M. Multidrug Treatment Using Kampo Medicine for Severe Fever with Thrombocytopenia Syndrome. Preprints 2025, 2025090637. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202509.0637.v1>
12. Ohe M. Commentary: Combination Treatment Using Favipiravir for Crimean-Congo Hemorrhagic Fever. <https://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.1594>
13. Ohe M. Treatment with Kampo medicine (*Keigai-rengyo-to* and *Sho-saiko-to*) with minocycline for Dengue virus. <https://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.3527>
14. Ohe M. Treatment with Kampo medicine (*Keigai-rengyo-to* or *Seijo-bofu-to*) and Doxycycline for Chikungunya virus infection. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.4177>
15. Ohe M. Treatment with Kampo medicine (*Keigai-rengyo-to* or *Seijo-bofu-to*) and Azithromycin for Zika virus infection. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.4321>

16. Ohe M. Treatment with Kampo medicine (Keigai-rengyo-to) and Minocycline for Respiratory syncytial virus infection. DOI:<http://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.3991>

Japanese names in roman characters (Chinese name for Pinyin)

JP: The Japanese Pharmacopoeia Ingredients and daily dosage

Kakkon-to (Ge Gen Tang) JP *Puerariae Radix* 4.0 g, JP *Ziziphus jujuba* 3.0 g,

JP *Ephedra Herba* 3.0 g, JP *Glycyrrhiza Radix* 2.0 g, JP *Cinnamomi Cortex* 2.0 g,

JP *Paeoniae Radix* 2.0 g, JP *Zingiberis Rhizoma* 2.0 g

Sho-saiko-to (Xiao Chai Hu Tang) JP *Bupleurum Radix* 7.0 g, JP *Pinellia Tuber* 5.0 g,

JP *Scutellariae Radix* 3.0, JP *Ziziphus jujuba* 3.0 g, JP *Panax ginseng* 3.0 g,

JP *Glycyrrhiza Radix* 2.0g, JP *Zingiberis Rhizoma* 1.0 g

Saiko-keishi-to (Chai Hu Gui Zhi Tang) JP *Bupleurum Radix* 5.0 g, JP *Pinellia Tuber* 4.0 g,

JP *Scutellariae Radix* 2.0 g, JP *Ziziphus jujuba* 2.0 g, JP *Panax ginseng* 2.0 g,

JP *Glycyrrhiza Radix* 2.0g, JP *Zingiberis Rhizoma* 1.0 g, JP *Cinnamomi Cortex* 2.0 g,

JP *Paeoniae Radix* 2.0 g

Keigai-rengyo-to (Jing Jie Lian Qiao Tang) JP *Scutellariae Radix* 1.5 g, JP *Schizonepetae Spica* 1.5g,
JP *Forsythiae Fructus* 1.5 g, JP *Coptidis Rhizoma* 1.5 g, JP *Platycodi Radix* 1.5 g,
JP *Aurantii Fructus Immaturus* 1.5 g, JP *Bupleurum Radix* 1.5 g, JP *Gardeniae Fructus* 1.5 g,
JP *Rehmanniae Radix* 1.5 g, JP *Menthae Herba* 1.5 g, JP *Paeoniae Radix* 1.5 g,
JP *Cnidii Rhizome* 1.5 g, JP *Angelicae Acutilobase Radix* 1.5 g, JP *Angelicae Dahuricae Radix* 1.5 g,
JP *Phellodendri Cortex* 1.5 g, JP *Glycyrrhiza Radix* 1.0 g, JP *Saposhnikoviae Radix* 1.5g

Seijo-bofu-to (Quing Shang Fang Feng Tang) JP *Scutellariae Radix* 2.5 g,
JP *Schizonepetae Spica* 1.0 g, JP *Forsythiae Fructus* 2.5 g, JP *Coptidis Rhizoma* 1.0 g,
JP *Platycodi Radix* 2.5 g, JP *Aurantii Fructus Immaturus* 1.0 g, JP *Gardeniae Fructus* 2.5 g,
JP *Cnidii Rhizome* 2.5 g, JP *Menthae Herba* 1.0 g, JP *Saposhnikoviae Radix* 2.5 g,
JP *Glycyrrhiza Radix* 1.0 g, JP *Angelicae Dahuricae Radix* 2.5 g

Table 1